

Conserving the “cheo cheo”: Where IT firm shares and information theory meet

AISDL Team

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This month, the AISDL Team was glad to see its continuing effort to raise the voice for conserving wildlife appearing in *Pacific Conservation Biology* (published by CSIRO/the Australian Academy of Science). The article stipulates the need for weaving humane values with scientific information, leveraging the sociocultural power to harmonize humans with nature [1].

The screenshot shows the journal's website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'HOME', 'BOOKS', 'JOURNALS', and 'LEARNING'. Below this is a banner for 'PACIFIC CONSERVATION BIOLOGY' with a subtitle 'A journal dedicated to conservation and wildlife management in the Pacific region.' and images of a turtle, a cactus, a bird, and flowers. A shopping cart icon indicates an empty cart, and a search bar is present. The breadcrumb trail reads 'You are here: Home > Journals > PC > Just Accepted > PC23058'. On the left, a sidebar lists 'JOURNAL HOME' (About the Journal, Editorial Structure, Publishing Policies, Contacts) and 'CONTENT' (Latest, Just Accepted, Most Read, Collections, All Content, Special Issues). The main content area features a 'Just Accepted' section with the text: 'This article has been peer reviewed and accepted for publication. It is in production and has not been edited, so may differ from the final published form.' Below this is the article title 'Call Vietnam mouse-deer “cheo cheo” and let the empathy save them from extinction: a conservation review and call for name change' by Quan-Hoang Vuong, Minh-Hoang Nguyen. An 'Abstract' section follows, starting with 'The rediscovery of the silver-backed chevrotain (Tragulus versicolor), an endemic species to Vietnam, in 2019 – after almost 30 years of being lost to science – is a remarkable outcome for conservation. Since its rediscovery, there has been significant concern for the conservation of the species due to hunting for'. A COPE logo is visible in the bottom right corner of the article area.

Illustration: Our article about conserving the *cheo cheo* [1]

The article articulates the coauthors' idea of building a funding source to contribute to the nature conservation cause by investing in some listed stocks. Technically, stocks we intend to invest in must possess some key features of (i) having significant growth potential, (ii) containing little environmental risk of potential moral-practical gaps in their CSR missions [2], and (iii) showing a certain degree of "relevance" with AISDL's fundamentals.

One of very few corporate stocks meeting these criteria is HPT (share code of HPT Corporation, on the UPCOM market). The firm has shown constant growth and anticipated rapidly increasing demand for cyber security services and smart IT products (see [3]). One noteworthy point is its relevance to our fundamental operation philosophy: information processing. Both HPT and AISDL have been working on important aspects of information processing, seeing its tremendous value in the future of humankind.

Coincidentally, the birthday of HPT Corp is the same as the publishing date of our MT title [4], i.e., January 13.

Bringing these values, intentional and unintentional, together, our investments in the cause of reducing the adverse impact of anthropogenic activities and conserving nature and wildlife now make sense [5]. We hope our undertaking will be actionable and fruitful, making strategic pursuits attainable.

References

[1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Call Vietnam mouse-deer "cheo cheo" and let the empathy save them from extinction: a conservation review and call for name change. *Pacific Conservation Biology*, 30, PC23058. <https://www.publish.csiro.au/PC/justaccepted/PC23058>

[2] Vuong QH, *et al.* (2021). Identifying the moral-practical gaps in corporate social responsibility missions of Vietnamese firms: An event-based analysis of sustainability feasibility. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(1), 30-41. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/csr.2029>

[3] HPT. (2020). HPT 25th Anniversary Ceremony. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6tH2fjvL1MA>

[4] Vuong QH. (2023). *Mindsponge Theory*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOC3WHZ2B3>

[5] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2023). Kingfisher: Contemplating the connection between nature and humans through science, art, literature, and lived experiences. *Pacific Conservation Biology*, 30(1), PC23044. <https://www.publish.csiro.au/PC/PC23044>

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